

CHALLENGES FACED BY STARTUPS AND THE WAYS TO OVERCOME THEM

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Annotatsiya. Ушбу мақола бугунги кунда стартаплар дуч келаётган кенг куламли муаммоларни ва бу муаммоларга ечим йулларини ва стратегияларини урганади. Муаллиф стартаплар дуч келадиган умумий муаммолар ва халқаро компаниялар дуч келадиган муаммоларни ва уларни хал қилиш йулларини келтириб утади ва бу сабабларни реал ҳаётда, жумладан, чакана савдо, озик-овкат, ишлаб чиқариш, фармацевтика ва тадбиркорлик соҳалари мисолида курсатиш учун амалий тадқиқотлар тақдим этади. Ушбу мақоланинг асосий мақсади- халқаро стартаплар дуч келадиган қийинчиликларни урганиш, буларни бартараф этиш йулларини урганиш ва натижаларини маҳаллий компаниялар билан солиштириш.

Kalit so'zlar: Кенг куламли муаммолар, стартап, чакана савдо, озик-овкат, ишлаб чиқариш, фармацевтика, тадбиркорлик, халқаро, маҳаллий.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматриваются общие проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются стартапы сегодня, а также пути и стратегии их преодоления. Автор приводит общие проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются стартапы, и проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются международные компании, и пути их решения, а также приводит примеры, иллюстрирующие эти причины в реальной жизни, включая примеры из розничной торговли, продуктов питания, производства, фармацевтики и предпринимательства. Основная цель этой статьи- изучить проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются международные стартапы, узнать способы преодоления этих проблем и сравнить результаты с результатами местных компаний.

Ключевые слова: Общие проблемы, стартапы, розничная торговля, продукты-питания, производства, фармацевтика, предпринимательство, международные, местные.

Abstract. This article explores the broad challenges facing startups today and explores ways and strategies to overcome these challenges. The author cites common challenges faced by startups and challenges faced by international companies and ways to solve them and provides case studies to illustrate these reasons in real life, including examples of retail, food, manufacturing, pharmacy, and entrepreneurs industries. is enough. The main purpose of this article is to study the challenges faced by international startups, learn ways to overcome these challenges, and compare the results with local companies.

Key words: Broad challenges, startups, retail, food, manufacturing, pharmacy, entrepreneurs, international, local.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This article is intended to explore the challenges that many startups are facing today and to plan in depth how to find solutions to them. First of all, startups are the type of business that started the voice business and went through the first stages in this business, and they are founded by one

or more people. In addition, the article analyzes the internal and external challenges faced by startups and how to overcome them. solution will be considered. The next part of the analysis discusses the problems faced by international startups and their solutions. In order to study this topic more deeply, in the next parts, a survey of local startups will be taken and analyzed; the survey mainly includes a deeper study of the problems faced by new entrepreneurs in various local industries and finding solutions to them. After all these studies, a general conclusion and recommendation will be given.

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this part, the challenges that startups often face are discussed, as well as the challenges faced by many international startups and how these startups have overcome these challenges are mentioned.

First of all, let's remember what kind of company a startup is. The word startup means a company in the early stages of its activity. This type of company is founded by one or more entrepreneurs. Also, such companies start with limited revenues and high costs when they start; they get capital from family members, investors, and venture capitalists. Startups take several years to reach high profits; during this time they face many difficulties, and some of them may even be closed during this period(Grant, 2021).

2.1 External challenges of startups

Many entrepreneurs face a number of external obstacles to success, and the reason for these external difficulties is the surrounding entrepreneurs, that is, the environmental factor. It also includes market prices, government rules and regulations, and competition. Some of these external challenges are as follows:

1. Competition. One of the biggest challenges for businesses these days is competition, and the competition is very tough and high these days, and if it's an online startup, the competition will be even tougher. It is not easy to compete in a competitive environment; there is always fierce competition in B2B and B2C organizations. Due to the increase in the number of new competitors every day, businesses may face different ideas, and this may cause the risk of losing customers. Being in constant motion, market trends and constant attraction of customers can be difficult for the company. But looking at it from another point of view, competition can be a good challenge for business development, because entrepreneurs constantly try to improve their products and services in order to find their place in the market. Through this, innovation is formed; it is easier to attract new customers. However, this is a difficult task for new entrepreneurs because they may not have enough experience to compete with experienced and established entrepreneurs(Haddin, 2018).

2. Finding customers and winning trust of customers. The next external factor is finding customers, which can also be difficult for new startups. Also, good customers can greatly contribute to the company's continued operations; good customers are loyal to the company and in some cases forgive them even if the company makes a mistake. In addition, customers' constant comments to the company will lead to positive changes in the company. After finding customers, gaining their trust is another difficult task for the company. Startups make progress thanks to

satisfied and loyal customers; customers are the real force in the company's success. Through their word of mouth, other customers come as new customers. In order to gain the trust and loyalty of customers, companies must work long and hard(Haddin, 2018).

3. Talent acquisition and retention. Another challenge for startups is attracting skilled employees and keeping them in the company, and this is one of the biggest problems in today's competitive market. Competing for the same talent with larger corporations and larger companies is more difficult and requires a more positive approach because these larger companies offer competitive salaries and benefits for skilled talent. The best way for startups to attract talent is to have a positive and supportive work environment and flexible working conditions, and startups can create opportunities and incentives for personal development just like large companies(Innovaction Global, 2024).

2.2 Internal challenges of startups

New entrepreneurs face many internal barriers to success, which are often called personal pressures and are experienced by the entrepreneur before starting a business. This section discusses internal problems that entrepreneurs may face.

1. Access to funding. One of the biggest challenges a new entrepreneur faces when starting a business is funding, and securing the capital needed to support business operations and growth is a constant challenge for startups with limited budgets and resources. The current economic conditions are tough, and the competition for investment and venture capital, as well as loans, is very high, which provides a wide choice for investors but creates problems for startups. It is also difficult to make the right decisions with limited funds, so they need well-thought-out and well-funded strategies because investors prefer to invest in well-established businesses because there is less risk(Innovaction Global, 2024).

2. Lack of planning. The next challenge is the lack of planning; many businesses fail because of poor planning. They may have planned but not covered everything or studied in detail. The most important developments—staffing, sales, and funding—will not be developed on the basis of a good plan, and in fact, all these are things that should be in the business plan from the beginning to the end of the business. Of course, not everything can be planned in advance, but when unexpected situations arise, entrepreneurs should know what to do. Sometimes the lack of necessary knowledge among entrepreneurs also causes these problems. This means that entrepreneurs should first get enough knowledge and then act for business(Scully, 2018).

3. Poor management. The next thing that startups can't afford is ineffective management; as startups grow, team management becomes more difficult, so it's important to have the right team members in place to make the right and clear decisions. must be. There are 2 main things to focus on when building a leadership team: the first is to make sure that the team is working together and to ensure transparency in the team when decisions are made. The second is to make sure the team is working well and make decisions based on results and solve problems faster. By having strong management, startups move in the right direction and succeed(Scully, 2018).

2.3 Challenges faced by international entrepreneurs

There are a lot of startups at the international level, and it is very difficult to consider all of them. but we can give examples of some companies; for example, Suno is an AI music generation

startup that allows people to create original music using AI, and the next one is Maisonette, which is an online market for children's clothes, accessories, and home decor that is sold. Another startup is Melio, a B2B payment platform that allows small businesses and suppliers to make payments easily. The next is FlowSpace, a platform that provides warehousing and logistics services for e-commerce businesses. These startup companies have also faced challenges, and we will look at them now. The first is competition; the reason is that when entering a new market, it will be difficult to compete with previously developed companies, and it is also difficult to attract customers because the brand was not yet known, especially in the e-commerce sector; this competition is now very high. The next challenge is to adapt to market changes. It is very difficult to adapt to changes in the current developing market; if the business does not carry out new ideas and research, it will be difficult to stay in the market. The next problem is funding, that is, the correct use and distribution of money. After finding investors, it is necessary to be able to use the investment correctly for the further development of the business; these are staff, sales, marketing, and similar sectors with money that includes support(Expert Panel, 2023).

2.4 How international startups overcome challenges

Startups have overcome the problems mentioned above. The first challenge was the competition; to overcome this, they chose niche targeting, that is, instead of serving everyone, they chose their target audience to support themselves and try to improve the customer experience. They also kept their creativity in order not to lag behind their competitors and always improved their markets and identified their competitive advantages, understood in which aspects their business differs from others, and acted accordingly. The next problem was to adapt to the changes in the market, and to solve this, the companies conducted continuous research, studied the market deeply and continuously, held discussions with their team members, and studied the opinions of customers. The next challenge is funding; for this, entrepreneurs first found investors or used their savings, made financial plans for proper use of funding, and increased their knowledge(Expert Panel, 2023).

3.0. RESEARCH METHODS

The purpose of this article was to study the challenges that cause the failure of many startups today and to learn ways to overcome these challenges, and to do this, the author used primary and secondary research methods. All information in the article was obtained from reliable sources. Information in the literature review was obtained and reviewed from electronic articles and statistical data. For some data, Google Scholar sourced it and used it, and it was taken from the 2020 and 2024 data there. A survey was conducted to learn how to overcome the difficulties faced by startups, and for this, question-and-answer interviews were used, and this was done online through Google Docs. Local startups participated in this survey. And the results of the survey were used in the next part of the analysis and discussions, and at the end of the article, it was concluded using all the collected data.

4.0. SURVEY

The author conducted a survey for startups; the purpose of this survey was to learn what difficulties startups faced when starting their business and how they overcame them. This survey covered 10 startups in different fields and asked their opinions. Also, startups in the food industry,

startups in the manufacturing industry, startups in the pharmacy industry, and several business owners participated in this survey. For example, the author went to supermarkets, pharmacies, and business owners to survey startups. The reason why the survey is carried out in different industries is that different companies have different problems, and the methods of solving them are also different. Among them, online surveys were conducted through docs.google.com/form/.

5.0. COLLECTING, ORGANIZING AND ANALYZING THE DATA

All online surveys were conducted to find out the opinion of startups. startups from different industries participated in it. They were asked 6 questions about their industry. If we start with the answers of startups in the first **retail industry**, when we asked them what challenges they faced, they answered funding, talent acquisition, competition, and team management. In the case of financing, they took money from banks and investors for the business and they used various discounts to attract customers. To solve the problems they faced, they first improved the planning and worked better with the team members to manage the team. The next industry is **pharmacy**, and the problems faced by startups in this industry are related to funding and competition, and they took capital for funding from family and loans. In order to overcome the challenges faced by the startups in this industry, they did good planning from the beginning, they learned to use the funding properly, and they spent the money in the right place. As for the **food industry**, a survey was taken from 2 large markets in this industry, and the answers show that the biggest challenges faced by these markets are funding, competition, and team management. 1 took money for market funding from family members, and the other took a loan from the bank and started the business. in order to attract customers in the new market, they offer various discounts. They used different methods to solve the problems they encountered; for example, they hired good employees based on their experience, conducted trainings with team members, and used cheaper prices than competitors. The next survey participants are **entrepreneurs** who have their own businesses; one of them is the owner of a furniture store, and one is an entrepreneur who runs a business in partnership. Based on the questions asked of them, the challenges that created problems for them were competition, funding, and finding good employees, because they used their own capital to start their business. used social media marketing and discounts to attract customers to the furniture store. Planning is the best way to overcome the challenges they face, and they train employees to work well. The last industry is **manufacturing**, and a survey was conducted in several startups in this industry. According to the results, the most important challenges faced by these startups are team management and talent acquisition. It was said that they had no problem with funding when opening the business because they used their own capital. There were some problems related to competition, and to overcome this, they made a new approach to their customers. In addition, they created a good salary and work environment for talent acquisition. and for team management, many trainings were conducted with team members separately.

6.0. DISCUSOION

All the information analyzed above shows that the problems faced by startups are different, and the ways and strategies to solve them are also different depending on the industry. The discussion of these data shows that the challenges that new businessmen, i.e., startups, may face have been considered, as well as the difficulties faced by other international startups at the beginning of their business and how they solved them. The most common problems faced by

international startups are competition, adaptation to market changes, and funding. In order to solve these problems, companies overcame the problems by improving the target, determining the target audience, determining their competitive advantages, and maintaining creativity in order not to fall behind the competition. Also, in order to adapt to market changes, they did constant market research, studied the market in depth, and conducted more conversations with team members, used their savings and investors to solve the funding problem when starting the business, and made a detailed business plan from the beginning. In addition, the local startups and the results of the survey were studied in the article. According to the survey, in order to study the problems of startups, problems were studied based on the experiences of various industries, including food, retail, manufacturing, pharmacy, and new businessmen, and the survey was conducted online and offline. According to the results of the survey, the most common challenges faced by startups in the **retail industry** are funding, talent acquisition, competition, and team management, and the most effective way to solve these problems is to find investors, give discounts to attract customers, and better work with team members. The next problems faced by the **pharmacy industry** are competition and funding. The way to solve this is with investors, loans, and good planning. As for the **food industry**, the challenges they face are competition and team management, and the solutions are giving discounts to customers and training employees more. The people surveyed are **new businessmen**; the problems they face are competition, funding, and finding good employees, and the solution is to use social media marketing to train employees well and attract more customers in competition. The last industry is **manufacturing**, and the problems encountered are talent acquisition and team management. To solve these problems, they created a good work environment for new employees and gave them high salaries, and for team management, they worked more with employees.

7.0. CONCLUSION

Based on this study, it can be said that it is important to study the challenges faced by startups and learn ways to overcome them at the time when the current competition is high and opening businesses is widespread. Based on the data and analysis, the most common challenges for startups are competition, funding, and adapting to market changes for international startups. The problems startups constantly face are competition, finding customers, talent acquisition and retention, access to funding, lack of planning, and poor management. To solve these problems, international startups use different ways, for example, identifying the target audience, conducting market research, conducting regular trainings with team members, and improving financial planning. According to the conducted survey, local startups in different industries face different problems and solve them in different ways. But if we summarize their answers, the 3 most common problems faced by local startups are competition, funding, and team management. Nowadays, of course, these problems are also widespread in international startups. The solutions they widely use vary depending on the industry, for example, training employees, finding investors for funding, and thoroughly studying the market for competition. If we make a recommendation based on the data, there are similarities in the problems of international and local startups, and the methods of overcoming them are somewhat similar. If they have, these startups will not fail in the future and will be able to properly study the problems and solve them appropriately.

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